

FORMATION OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES BASED ON TETRAGONAL ZIRCONIA DOPED BY D-ELEMENTS OF I GROUP

Ass. Prof. Dr. Gorban O.¹, M.Sc. Kharchenko M.¹, M.Sc. Bryukhanova I.I., Ass. Prof. Dr Gorban S.¹, M.Sc. E. Sinelnikova²

Donetsk institute for physics and engineering named after O.O. Galkin NAS of Ukraine, Ukraine¹
Municipal educational institution the Gymnasium №4, Russia²

oxanag1@ukr.net

Abstract: The investigation of influence of modified conditions on formation of complex materials based on tetragonal zirconia doped by d-elements of I group (Cu or Ag) was carried out, in particular the routes of synthesis and type of dopant. The kinetic parameters of separated stage of NPs formation (drying of hydrogel under MW irradiation, dehydration and crystallization of amorphous zirconia NPs) were estimated. It was shown, the dehydration of tetragonal zirconia hydrogel in conditions of MW irradiation occurs due in two stage. In contrast for Cu (or Ag) –modified hydrogels only one stage dehydration is observed. The dehydration and crystallization of unmodified and modified xerogel is studied by DSC method. It was shown that the kinetic parameters of dehydration depend as from nature of zirconium salts that were using for synthesis and type of dopant. For crystallization processes the some parameters (crystallization temperature, enthalpy) are saved features of dependence on route of synthesis for unmodified and modified systems. However, the behaviour of dependence of activation energy on route of synthesis is contrast for unmodified and modified systems.

Keywords: COMPOSITE NANOPARTICLES, DSC, DEHYDRATION, CRYSTALLIZATION

1. Introduction

Complex oxide systems based on zirconia are promising materials in modern material science [1]. Reasons for using of d-elements of I group (Cu, Ag, Au) or their oxides at technology of creation of functional composite oxide structure are next:

- the first these metals and their oxides have bactericide and fungicide properties,
- the second they have some electrical and optical properties,
- the third they can be used as catalysts and
- the fourth they can be used at creation ceramic materials with higher tribological properties [2-3].

Some routes of creation of functional structures are used in material science technology. In practice, the impregnation of Ag or Cu salts in oxide surface is a more often used method for creation or enhance catalytic systems [4]. However, introducing of Cu or Ag-contained compounds into the oxide synthesis process results in a greater variation of catalytic system properties because, in this case, the added ions influence not only the surface state but also the crystal lattice of the oxide [5].

However, the using of second route of synthesis for creation of composite structure based on tetragonal zirconia doped by d-elements of I group (especially, Cu and Ag) has determined features. The use of ammonium hydrate as agent-precipitator leads to form Cu (or Ag) ammonium hydroxocomplexes that occlude on surface of colloidal zirconia hydroxide nanoparticles (NPs) [6]. There are the ammonium complexes of copper - $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_m(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]^{2+}$ or hydroxocomplexes - $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_m(\text{OH})_k]^{2-k}$, where coordination number of copper is 4 or 6 and $k < 3$, or mixing ammonium hydroxocomplexes - $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_m(\text{OH})_k]^{2-k}$. For case of silver complexes in which coordination number of silver ions is 2 the structure of complexes may be described as $[\text{Ag}(\text{NH}_3)_2]\text{X}$, where X is chloride ion or nitrate ion. Ammonium molecule in first coordination sphere may be exchange on water molecule in water solution. The structures of copper or silver complexes depend on synthesis conditions, in particular, pH precipitation. For example, at high pH the formation of ammonium complexes of copper or silver are observed, such as the decreasing of pH value of solution leads to exchange of ammonium ligand on hydroxyl group. Since zirconia hydrogel is colloid systems the absorption of copper or silver complexes on zirconia NPs surface may influence on formation of

modified NPs systems and their properties.

The nature of zirconium salts may change the optimal concentration and viscosity of solution. It also is very important moment in technology of obtaining of complex oxide systems because it may influence on distribution the dopants between phases and leads to form inhomogeneity product [7]. Other main moments of wet technology of complex oxide materials are influence of type of dopant, salt nature and salt concentration on emulsion stability, aggregation and electrophoretic movement of NPs, features of formation precipitates [8-10], phase stability of NPs, other. In this connection, in technologies of obtaining of complex oxide materials investigators do accent the influence of these factors on drying of zirconia hydrogel, dehydration and crystallization amorphous zirconia xerogel, growth of oxide NPs.

The aim of present work is investigation of formation of complex oxide systems based on tetragonal zirconia doped d-elements of I group.

2. Preconditions and means for resolving problems

2.1 Synthesis and characterization of zirconia metastable NPs

Fig. 1 shows the scheme of syntheses of tetragonal zirconia doped by copper or silver dopant. Synthesis contains some stages there are zirconia hydrogel precipitation; formation of amorphous zirconium hydroxide (xerogel) under MW drying; formation of composite structure based on tetragonal zirconia under heat treatment.

Fig. 1 - Scheme of syntheses of tetragonal zirconia doped by copper or silver dopant.

Dehydration kinetics of zirconia hydrogel and xerogel are described in Avrami-Erofeev approach:

$$d\alpha/dt = k \cdot f(\alpha) \quad (1)$$

where α is the share conversion of phase fraction, t – dehydration time (min), $f(\alpha)$ – function which depends on dehydration or crystallization mechanism and NPs geometry [11]. Equation (1) after integration is:

$$g(\alpha) = \int d\alpha / f(\alpha) = k \cdot dt = kt \quad (2)$$

where $g(\alpha)$ is function which depends on dehydration or crystallization mechanism such as $f(\alpha)$. The types of $g(\alpha)$ are shown in work [11].

Accordingly [11], type of function which describes dehydration kinetic depends on partial pressure of water under NPs surface. The constant removing of water vapor is characteristic for MW conditions of drying of zirconia hydrogel, because $g(\alpha)$ corresponds to Avrami-Erofeev equation $[-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/n}$, where $n=0.5; 1; 2; 2.5; 3; \dots$, and equation (2) transform to (3):

$$[-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/n} = kt \quad (3)$$

Avrami constant n shows mechanism of process (dehydration and crystallization), and $\ln K$ corresponds to velocity of evaporation or crystallization.

Activation energies of dehydration and crystallization are estimated in Kissinger approach (4):

$$d \ln(\beta/T_{max}^2) / d(1/T_{max}) = -E_{act} / R \quad (4)$$

where T_{max} – temperature of maximum of endothermic or exothermic peaks, K , β is heat increasing rate.

3 Kinetic parameters of formation of xerogels and processes of their dehydration and crystallization

3.1 Kinetic parameters of drying of hydrogel under MW condition

Analysis TG data in logarithmic coordinates of equation (3) allows to estimate parameters of dehydration there are m which describes reaction mechanism (in particular, if $m < 1$ the evaporation occurs according to homogenous mechanism, if m changes from 1 to 2 the evaporation occurs with line portion of surface, for example from pores) and $\ln K$ corresponds to rate of evaporation.

It is noted, that dehydration process is sum of water diffusion processes on surface and inside pores of hydrogel NPs, water phase transformation (liquid-vapor), water desorption from NPs surface and other. For example, dehydration process of Cu doped tetragonal zirconia hydrogel approximately may be determined as:

For Ag doped zirconia process of dehydration is analogical. The amount of residual ammonium, nitrate or chloride ions depends on precursor type and may be varied by washing number. Thus, the process which occurs at dehydration may be complex because the dehydration determines by water desorption from pores surface and water diffusion from pores to NPs surface.

Parameters of kinetic dehydration of unmodified and Cu (or Ag) modified zirconia hydrogel which syntheses from zirconium nitrate and chloride salts were shown in table 1.

Table 1 – Kinetic parameters of unmodified (ZrO₂-3 mol. % Y₂O₃) and Cu (or Ag) modified amorphous xerogel formation (ZrO₂-3 mol. % Y₂O₃- 1 mol. % CuO (or Ag₂O))

	ZrO(OH) ₂ -3 mol.%Y(OH) ₃ -x mol. % Me-complex		
		Me - CuO	Ag ₂ O
	0	1	1
Nitrate route			
lnk1	-4.62	-2.86	-2.33
n1	1.99	2.01	2.5
lnk2	-2.32		-
n2	0.81		-
Chloride route			
lnk1	-4.8	-2.14	-2.49
n1	1.90	2.04	2.6
lnk2	-2.61		-
n2	0.82		-

It was shown that the dehydration of unmodified zirconia xerogel contains two stages, the kinetic parameters of that depend on precursor nature. The n_1 values for systems is near 2 for both routes of synthesis of zirconia hydrogel. It is evidence that the evaporation occurs with line portion of surface and the nature of used zirconia salt does not practically influence on intensity of water evaporation. The n_2 values m is less than 1 for both routes of synthesis of zirconia hydrogel. The change of n values at transfer from first to second stage may be connected with activation of diffusion processes on second stage. Kinetic of second stage may be described by homogenous mechanism of evaporation and intensity of this stage in two time bigger than evaporation water on first stage.

For cause of Cu (or Ag) modified zirconia hydrogel the dehydration occurs on the one stage. The n is approximately equal 2 and the mechanism of dehydration of zirconia hydrogel does not change at their modification by Cu ions. For Ag-modified systems n is above 2. The intensity of evaporation for both type of dopants is bigger to compare with intensity of unmodified systems and does not depend from type of dopants that use for creation of complex system.

Thus, mechanism evaporation for first stage is equal for unmodified and Cu (or Ag) modified tetragonal zirconia but the modification of tetragonal zirconia by d-elements of I group lead to disappearance the second stage of evaporation. The rate of dehydration process is more intensive for case modified systems at approximately equal time of drying. The estimated kinetic parameters show the independence of dehydration of modified zirconia hydrogel on nature of synthesis route and type of dopant.

3.2 Kinetic parameters of dehydration of xerogel

Fig.2 shows the DSC curves for unmodified and Cu (or Ag) modified tetragonal zirconia.

Fig.2 DSC curves for nitrate route: 1) unmodified 3) Cu and 5) Ag modified tetragonal zirconia and for chloride route: 4) unmodified 3) Cu and 6) Ag modified tetragonal zirconia.

Accordingly DSC data at calcination of unmodified system are observed the wide endothermic peak (temperature diapason is 20-250°C) and the narrow exothermic peak at temperature above 400°C. For case of Cu(Ag)-modified systems DSC specters shows the wide endothermic peak (temperature range is 20-250°C) and two exothermic peaks. First exothermic peak is appearance at near 300°C and their intensity depends on precursor nature. This peak corresponds to processes that occur at destroyed or structure reorganization of Cu (or Ag) complexes. Second exothermic peak correspond to crystallization of tetragonal zirconia. Kinetic parameters of dehydration of xerogel are presented in table 2.

Table 2 - Kinetic parameters of dehydration of xerogel

Systems	Parameters	
	T, °C	ΔH, J/g
Chloride route		
ZrO ₂ -3Y ₂ O ₃	383,2	-449,44
ZrO ₂ -3Y ₂ O ₃ -1CuO	378,8	-544,04
ZrO ₂ -3Y ₂ O ₃ -1Ag ₂ O	393,1	-454.51
Nitrate route		
ZrO ₂ -3Y ₂ O ₃	379	-565.81
ZrO ₂ -3Y ₂ O ₃ -1CuO	382.9	-779.04
ZrO ₂ -3Y ₂ O ₃ -1Ag ₂ O	401.9	-519.7

It is noted, that for unmodified systems the temperatures of dehydration is decreasing for material, which was synthesized by nitrate route. However, the enthalpy of this process are increasing for this route. It connects with the adding of energy expensive at remove residual nitrate groups to dehydration of xerogel.

For Cu (or Ag) modified systems the shift of maximum of temperature of dehydration to higher temperature are observed and the increasing of enthalpy are occurred. It is noted, for Cu modified systems the route of synthesis influences on parameters of dehydration and as for unmodified systems.

The estimated of activation energies according to equation (4) for dehydration process are presented in table 3.

Table 3 Activation energy of dehydration for unmodified and Cu(or Ag) modified system.

Route of synthesis	Zr(OH)2-3 mol.% Y(OH)3-x mol. % M-complex		
		CuO, %	Ag ₂ O, %
	0	1	1
	Activation energy, kJ/mol		
Nitrate	22.1	29.56	40.32
Chloride	37.2	25.06	19.71

Analysis of activation energy show that adding of d-elements of I group leads to decrease of activation energy values. It may be connected with change of structure of hydrate shell of modified NPs.

First exothermic peak is appearance at 257°C (for Cu-modified systems, ΔH=103 J/g) and 253°C (for Ag-modified systems, ΔH=105 J/g) for systems that are synthesized by

nitrate route and at 263°C (for Cu-modified systems, $\Delta H=76$ J/g) and 263°C (for Ag-modified systems, $\Delta H=55$ J/g) for systems that are synthesized by chloride route. The difference in enthalpy of this process for systems which are synthesized by different routes may be connected with features of Cu (or Ag) complex structures, in particular, with different ligands.

3.3 Kinetic parameters of crystallization of xerogel

Kinetic parameters of dehydration of xerogel are presented in table 4.

Table 4 - Kinetic parameters of crystallization of xerogel

Systems	Parameters	
	T, °C	ΔH , J/g
Chloride route		
ZrO ₂ -3Y ₂ O ₃	699,7	108,04
ZrO ₂ -3Y ₂ O ₃ -1CuO	713,4	131,17
ZrO ₂ -3Y ₂ O ₃ -1Ag ₂ O	715,2	107,0
Nitrate route		
ZrO ₂ -3Y ₂ O ₃	710,9	122,81
ZrO ₂ -3Y ₂ O ₃ -1CuO	728,1	165,05
ZrO ₂ -3Y ₂ O ₃ -1Ag ₂ O	720,4	109,4

As we can see from table 4, the crystallization temperatures are higher for systems that are synthesized by nitrate route independently from their chemical composition. It is also noted the enthalpies of systems that are synthesized by nitrate route are higher than for systems are synthesized by chloride route. Higher values of enthalpy evidence about most defectiveness of crystal lattice of tetragonal zirconia. For case of Cu-modified tetragonal zirconia the routes of preparation influence on parameters of crystallization and ordering of structures are strongly.

The estimated of activation energies according to equation (4) for crystallization process are presented in table 5.

Table 5 Activation energy of crystallization for unmodified and Cu(or Ag) modified system.

Route of synthesis	ZrO(OH)2-3 mol.% Y(OH)3-x mol. % M-complex		
		CuO, %	Ag ₂ O, %
	0	1	1
	Activation energy, kJ/mol		
Nitrate	348,70	243,08	233
Chloride	544,38	230,59	151

Analysis of estimated activation energies show the difference dependence of E_{akt} on route of synthesis for unmodified and modified systems. For unmodified system that is synthesized by chloride route the activation energy is approximately in two time higher than for one that are synthesized by nitrate route. In contrast, the modified systems shows dependence on as route of synthesis and type of dopant (Cu or Ag).

4 Conclusion

It was shown that surface Cu (or Ag) modification of tetragonal zirconia which are obtained by wet technology occurs due to adsorption of complex of these d-elements. It was shown the structure of complex depends on synthesis conditions (route) and nature of dopants. Based on DSC method the formation oxide NPs is investigated. It was found the appearance of addition exothermic peak in DSC spectra of modified systems. This peak connects with presence of ammonium or hydroxocomplexes on zirconia NPs surface. It was noted the type of dopants and synthesis route more influence on kinetic parameters of dehydration. It may be connection with different stability of complex with different structures at temperature less 300°C. Other side the dependence of activation energy of crystallization on route of synthesis and nature of dopants is very strongly.

Acknowledgment

The work was carried out in framework of projects NANOGUARD 2AR HORIZON 2020 and partially in framework projects N47/16-H of program NAS of Ukraine "Fundamental problem of creation of new materials and nanotechnologies"

Reference

- Ju-Nam Yon Manufactured nanoparticles: An overview of their chemistry, interactions and potential environmental implications. *Science of The Total Environment*, 2008, 400, 396-414 (Yon Ju-Nam, Jamie R. Lead).
- Díaz-Flores L.L. Formation of Ag-Cu Nanoparticles in SiO₂ Films by Sol-Gel Process and their Effect on the Film Properties. *Phys. Stat. Sol. C*, 2007, 4 (N6), 2016–2020 (L.L. Díaz-Flores, M.G. Garnica-Romo, J. González-Hernández, J.M. Yáñez-Limón, P. Vorobiev, and Y. V. Vorobiev).
- Mayo M. J. Surface chemistry effects on the processing and superplastic properties of nanocrystalline oxide ceramics. *Nanostruct. Mater.*, 1999, 11(2), 271–282 (Mayo M. J., Seidensticker J. R., Hauge D. C., Carim A. H.).
- Kundokovic Lj. Deep oxidation of methane over zirconia supported Ag catalysts. *Applied Catalysis A: General*, 1999, 183, 35-51 (Kundokovic Lj., Flytrani-Stephanopoulos M.).
- Ramaswamy Veda. Structural and spectral features of nano-crystalline copper-stabilized zirconia. *Catalysis Today*, 2004, 97, 63–70 (Veda Ramaswamy, Mahesh Bhagwat, Darbha Srinivas, Arumugamangalam V. Ramaswamy).
- Ануфриенко, В.Ф. Особенности ассоциирования ионов Cu(II) в концентрированных водно-аммиачных растворах азотнокислой меди по данным ЭПР. *ДАН*, 2011, 440 (№5), 651-654 (В.Ф. Ануфриенко, Г.А.Зенковец, Р.А. Шутилов, В.Ю. Гаврилов, Н.Т. Васенин, А.А.Шубин, З.Р. Исмагилов, В.Н. Пармон).
- Cousin P. Preparation of mixed oxides: A review. *Mater. Sci. and Engineer.*, 1990, A130 (N 2), 119-125 (P. Cousin, R.A. Ross).
- Carter Geoffrey A. Ammonia-induced precipitation of zirconyl chloride and zirconyl -yttrium chloride solutions under industrially relevant conditions. *Powder Technology*, 2009, 188, 222-228 (Geoffrey A. Carter, Mark I. Ogden, Craig E. Buckley, Clinton Maitland, Mark Paskevicius).
- Chuah G.K. The influence of preparation conditions on the surface area of zirconia. *Applied Catalysis A*, 1996, 145 (1-2), 267-284 (G.K. Chuah, S. Jaenicke, S.A. Cheonga and K.S. Chana).
- Konstantinova T. Mesoscopic phenomena in oxide nanoparticles systems: processes of growth *J. Nanopart. Res.* – 2011. - V.13. – P. 4015-4023 (Konstantinova, T., I. Danilenko, V. Glazunova, G. Volkova, O. Gorban)
- Masudo, Yoshio The effect of the water vapor pressure on the kinetics of the thermal dehydration of some hydrates. Examples of magnesium, manganese, cobalt, zinc, yttrium and erbium formate dihydretes. *Netsu Sokutei*, 1995, 22 (N4), 203-211 (Yoshio Masudo).